

Communicating Operational Reliability Requirements to Designers

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Abstract

Combat forces need reliable equipment in order to have a high state of readiness and a high probability of successfully performing their missions. Past experience has shown that fielded systems generally fall short of needed reliability characteristics. This paper summarizes previous studies that have identified possible reasons for reliability shortfalls, and proposes an additional cause - the inability to properly communicate the real user reliability concerns to designers.

Background.

Our combat forces generally have modern, technologically superior weapon systems. However, with time, we need to develop and acquire new systems or modify existing ones to remain combat ready. Air Force Regulation 57-1 describes the process for operational commands in the Air Force to develop, document and process requirements for new or modified systems (Ref 1). Three documents are used to describe user needs and system characteristics.

Mission Needs Statement (MNS)

Overall mission needs are stated in the MNS. These needs are in broad terms that relate to specific assigned mission areas. Trade studies are then performed to identify the best candidate system to satisfy user's overall needs.

Operational Requirements Document (ORD)

Once the candidate system is selected, the detailed performance characteristics of the system, including **operational reliability and maintainability (R&M) requirements and**

objectives such as mission reliability, mission capable rate, break rate, and mean time between maintenance are documented in the ORD. These and other recommended operational R&M terms are described in Air Force Pamphlet 57-9 (Ref 2). Note that these R&M requirements are in terms of **operational, not contractual R&M characteristics** - these requirements are expressed in ways that are meaningful to the **operations, maintenance, and support communities.**

Requirements Correlation Matrix (RCM)

A third document, the RCM, summarizes the more important **operational requirements** in the ORD and correlates them with the **associated contractual requirements**. In theory, if the contractual requirements are accurately derived from operational requirements and achieved during the engineering and manufacturing development phase of a program, the resulting product should satisfy the user's operational requirements. The reason for the existence of the RCM stems from experience that shows that operational R&M needs, especially reliability of avionics, are frequently not achieved.

Reliability Shortfall Examples

A number of studies have been performed over the past two decades that highlight the shortfall problem. In 1976 George Kern studied 16 avionics units and compared the contractual requirement, predicted value and contractually demonstrated value to the achieved, comparable field reliability characteristic. Of the 16 units studied, 14 failed to achieve a field reliability characteristic equal to or greater than any of the three contractual values (Ref 3).

During pre-production flight testing of the F-16 in the late 70s, the aircraft demonstrated a contractual system mean time between failure (MTBF) of 2.5 hours. However, the comparable operational reliability measure, mean time between maintenance - inherent (MTBM-Inh) was only 0.83 (Ref 4). Even after 18 months of operation in the field, the MTBM-Inh was still less than 1.6 hours as compared to the "demonstrated" 2.5 hour MTBF.

The APG-66 radar system used on the F-16 had a similar history. This radar had a production requirement of 97 hours MTBF and formally demonstrated that requirement in a simulated environment (Ref 5). However, the radar subsystem only achieved 14 hours MTBM-Inh in 1980 and was only 80 hours in 1985.

Why the Reliability Shortfall?

A number of reasons for the shortfall problem have been suggested. In the 70s, the statistics associated with MIL-STD-781B tests related the **upper test MTBF** with the specification Section 3 requirement. This resulted in demonstrating characteristics that were only 1/3 to 1/2 of the specification requirements. This deficiency was corrected in 1977 with the publication of MIL-STD-781C. This revised standard related the **lower test MTBF** to the Section 3 requirement (Ref 6).

Lack of appropriate environments in laboratory testing was also identified as a possible cause. In the late 70s and early 80s, the Air Force Flight Dynamics Laboratory conducted extensive testing of avionics to "evaluate the effectiveness of CERT [Combined Environments Reliability Testing] for the early identification of deficiencies and insight into how the [avionics] equipment will **perform in operational service**" (Ref 7). Since then, CERT-type environments have commonly been used in chamber-based reliability demonstrations.

Some equipments were not properly "debugged" prior to being fielded. For example, the F-16 radar took five years to grow from 14 to 80 hours MTBM-Inh in the field. The DoD strongly supports reliability growth or test-analyze-and-fix (TAAF) programs to "surface these [reliability] problems early and eliminate them before rate production" (Ref 8).

And finally, the existence of warranties, especially reliability improvement warranties is another indication of our inability to initially deliver products with needed/desired field reliability characteristics.

Relating Operational and Contractual R&M Characteristics

Rome Laboratory (formerly Rome Air Development Center) has funded two studies in the 80s that attempt to correlate contractual reliability characteristics with operational reliability performance (Refs 9, 10). These studies analyze field reliability characteristics (e.g., Mean Time Between Maintenance - Inherent) with the corresponding contractual reliability values (e.g., contractual requirement, predicted value, and demonstrated value). The relationship formulas from these studies are frequently referred to as "Translators." Although the primary purpose of these translators was to provide a tool to project R&M characteristics, the statistical results of these studies also provide an insight into the variability of the data used in the studies.

For example, the 1989 study considered a broad data base of electronic equipment and considered variables such as the type of host platform (e.g., fighter, transport), the type of equipment functions (e.g., radar, communications), and the number of mission/on-off cycles (Ref 10). However, even with these considerations, the reliability translators produce large variances of the estimates. For example, the fighter avionics translators that relate three different field reliability characteristics to the demonstrated MTBF value all have a standard error of the estimate that is greater than 1.0 and a mean absolute error that is greater than 0.8. This latter statistic means that an estimate derived from these translators will be in error by approximately plus or minus 80 percent, on the average.

The relatively high variability of this latest translator suggests that perhaps some other, important variable has not been considered. The purpose of this paper is to suggest that a critical missing variable is the effectiveness of the definition for failure in contractual specifications.

Definition of "Failure"

MIL-STD-721C defines reliability as:

- (1) The duration or probability of failure-free performance under stated conditions, or
- (2) The probability that an item can perform its intended function for a specified interval under stated conditions. (Ref 11)

These two definitions are good in that they define several of the variables that have an effect on reliability characteristics, namely mission duration and conditions (e.g., environmental stresses). In fact, these are the variables that have been addressed to date in the RADC translator studies. However, these two definitions focus primarily on the equipment **functional** characteristics, not on the effects that result from a variety of equipment **malfunctions**. The recently published DoDI 5000.2 defines reliability with an additional emphasis:

The ability of a system and its parts to perform its mission without failure, degradation, or demand on the support system. (Ref 12)

Rather than focusing on equipment functions, this definition focuses on the effects that malfunctions can have on the **mission** and the **support system** (i.e., requirements for manpower, spares, support equipment, etc.). Most of the equipment considered in the translator studies "demonstrated" the specification requirements. However, many of the malfunctions that occur in a reliability demonstration are classified as non-chargeable or non relevant for various reasons. In many cases the classifications are based on the definition of "failure" in the specification or the formal test document. The author has seen many specifications and test documents which list criteria that exclude selected malfunctions, many of which would be reported as a "failure" in the field. In the 1976 Hughes study of 16 avionics items, approximately 70% of the malfunctions observed during formal reliability demonstrations were classified as "non-relevant."

A Classroom Exercise

For the past five years, I have been using an exercise in class to illustrate the importance of considering "effects" in the definition of "failure." I have developed a list of 26 carefully constructed events, most of which describe actual events that have occurred in test programs or in the field (See appendix). I divide the class into as many as six smaller groups and ask each group to review and determine how many of the 26 events are "failures." To illustrate several points, each group is assigned a different perspective. Table 1 lists the six perspectives and the typical range of "failures" reported by each group.

Table 1

Failure Definition Exercise	
Group Perspective	"Failures"
Operators of the equipment	12-15
Technicians who perform on-equipment maintenance	19-26
Personnel at an Air Logistics Center	10-18
The system program office (SPO)	5-15
Prime contractor	0-5
Subcontractors/vendors	0-5

The class discussion that follows shows that, in general, the top three groups developed classification criteria based upon **effects**. For example, the operators are typically concerned about safety and the ability to accomplish the mission; the maintenance technicians are concerned about unscheduled maintenance. On the other hand the two contractor groups are primarily concerned about legal responsibility - "It's not my fault." Almost invariably, the contractor group's primary reference for responsibility is the contract specification.

Note that the number of SPO failures generally falls somewhere between the effects groups and the spec groups. The SPO groups are occasionally concerned about

the users, but are generally more concerned about the specification. In either case, the exercise illustrates how there might be a significant gap between the field expectations and the delivered product.

It is the author's opinion that one of the major reasons that we do not field systems that satisfy user expectations, is that we do not adequately communicate the user perspective and expectations to the designers. I believe that most designers want to develop a product that satisfies the user's need. However, many have limited field experience and do not truly understand what is expected. During a "Blue-Two" visit, a mechanical engineer said:

"This is only the second time I've been to an Air Force Base in my 30-year career. And I don't think that's unusual. Mostly the designers will visit the manufacturer or the company that is making the equipment, but rarely - if ever - the user." (Ref 13)

If the above quote is representative of many design engineers, then their only guidance for designing reliability into equipment is the system/item specification. That specification typically contains a requirement for x hours mean time between failure - MTBF. But unless defined, the term MTBF and specifically the term "failure" can mean different things to different people as illustrated in the above classroom exercise. Therefore, we need to have a good specification that will communicate the needs of the users (operators, maintainers, logistics support) to the SPO, from the SPO to the prime contractor, and from the prime contractor to those supporting subcontractors and vendors that actually perform the design function.

To create a communication bridge from the users to the designers, I am suggesting that program offices, **with assistance from the operators, maintenance technicians, and logistics support personnel**, develop an effect-related definition for "failure" to be included in specifications. The following is the author's attempt to develop such a definition, including two important ground rules and some exceptions. Part of this definition is based on MIL-STD-781D which contains a section that addresses definition of failure. The definition is "generic" and should be tailored for a particular program.

Suggested Specification Definition for "Failure"

A failure is any condition in which delivered hardware and/or software that is developed, manufactured, procured, or integrated by the contractor does not perform required functions in accordance with Section 3 of the applicable specification or the operators manual, and which has one or more of the following effects:

a. As a result of observed or otherwise indicated conditions (e.g., built-in-test (BIT)), the operator must make additional decisions and/or take action in order to accomplish the mission or assure safety of the system. Included are documented "false alarms" - situations where a malfunction is indicated (e.g., BIT), the operator makes a judgment that a malfunction does not exist, but the operator considers the false alarms to adversely affect his ability to perform the mission. [These operator observed events may be reported in the field as Code 2, Code 3, or Code 4 "breaks" depending upon the severity of the effects. The operational terms "Break Rate" and mean time between mission critical failure (MTBMCF) are derived from these effect-related reports.]

b. The end item/system is officially categorized as "down" or unavailable for operation or for a like mission until observed and/or indicated conditions are evaluated. [These downing events are used to quantify availability characteristic such as operational availability, mission capable rate, and mean down time.]

c. Maintenance personnel are required to expend time to assess and/or correct conditions documented by the operators or by maintenance personnel. Also included are maintenance actions resulting from time change requirements directed by technical orders. [All corrective maintenance events must be considered when trying to quantify maintenance effort (e.g., maintenance manhours/flight hour) or manpower levels.]

d. Material is consumed (bolts, safety wire, sealant, piece parts, etc.) and/or replacement of reparable items (LRUs, SRUs, etc.) is required. [These replacement events are used to compute terms such as mean time between removal (MTBR), a term related to the need for replacement items (spares).]

IMPORTANT GROUND RULE NUMBER 1: Malfunctions shall not be excluded as a result of additional information discovered during maintenance or later failure analysis. The nature of resulting maintenance actions DOES NOT CHANGE THE OBSERVED EFFECT. For example maintenance may respond to a reported malfunction that causes the system to be down. Even though the technician cannot duplicate (CND) the malfunction on the end item, or a removed item bench checks serviceable (BCS) in the shop, the system is still not available. [Note that approximately 10% of all reported on-aircraft corrective maintenance actions are CNDs, and 20-30% of all unscheduled avionics removals for cause result in a BCS (or retest OK - RTOK)!]

IMPORTANT GROUND RULE NUMBER 2: Malfunctions shall not be excluded as a result of proposed or after-the-fact fixes, even if these fixes are verified as being effective. [The purpose of a demonstration is to verify the reliability characteristics of a sample of the overall population. If the sample is representative, then the number of failures should also be representative. An effective design change will improve those specific items under test in the same way that specific items are improved in a test-analyze-and-fix program. However, these fixes DO NOT correct other, different failure mechanisms that exist on other units that have not yet been tested. The logic of this ground rule can be tested by looking at a theoretical situation where ALL observed hardware and software malfunctions observed during a demonstration are fixed and are excluded as failures. The resulting calculations would then show a zero failure rate or an infinite MTBF. I doubt that any one would make decisions that are based on assuming a unit with perfect reliability.]

EXCLUSIONS - Events not to be considered as failures:

Conditions resulting from operating the system/equipment in physical environments beyond the limits in the specification.

Conditions resulting from operating the system/equipment in a manner that is prohibited by the operator's manual or by other established guidance.

Conditions resulting from handling, maintaining, storing, or transporting the system/equipment in a manner that is not in

accordance with technical orders or other established guidance.

Communicating to the Designer

The goal of the above definition is to convey to designers more than just the functional requirements stated in the specification. It also describes the negative effects of "failures" upon the operator, maintainer and logisticians as they perceive them. With this definition, the designer now has a more complete perspective of those factors that he or she must consider during the design process. For example, a CND can result from a sensitive built-in-test circuit. The designer, knowing that a CND is a failure, must balance his hardware/software design to satisfy the need for accurate built-in-test accuracy (a functional requirement) with the need to reduce/eliminate erroneous failure indications (a field need). A BCS/RTOK can result from different test strategies used in the built-in-test and the shop test equipment. If designers know that BCS/RTOKs count as failures, they will need to assure compatibility between the built-in-test and external test equipment.

Communicating to the Manufacturing Community

Likewise, the above definition should also convey to manufacturing personnel that the quality of their product has an impact on "failures." For example, a CND or an intermittent condition could be caused by a poor solder joint or other connection. There are no exclusions as a result of poor workmanship, using the wrong part, or having a process out of control.

Summary

I believe that we can improve the reliability of new systems if we can communicate the concerns of operators, maintainers and logistics support personnel to design and manufacturing personnel. One means to communicate these concerns is through the development of a comprehensive definition for failure that is related to the field "effects" that are inherent in the user's operational reliability characteristics stated in the ORD and RCM. This definition can also help preserve the integrity of the sampling and demonstrating process by not allowing exclusions on the basis of after-the-fact or proposed fixes.

References

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APPENDIX - FAILURE DEFINITION EXERCISE

- _____ 1. A brake assembly malfunctioned, resulting in a hot brake. Failure analysis showed that the brake was incorrectly assembled by a government technician.
- _____ 2. A computer malfunctioned and was replaced. Shop technicians found sand in the unit.
- _____ 3. Built-in-test indicated a malfunction in the fire warning subsystem. Maintenance could not duplicate the malfunction.
- _____ 4. The single engine flamed out, but was restarted OK.
- _____ 5. A bird strike resulted in five damaged engine fan blades.
- _____ 6. The master caution indicator did not illuminate during preflight. A bad light bulb was replaced in 5 minutes.
- _____ 7. Built-in-test indicated a malfunction in a redundant navigation system. The malfunction could not be duplicated by the line technician.
- _____ 8. The radar transmitter, removed as "weak", was sent to the depot where the unit tested OK.
- _____ 9. The radio malfunctioned. Failure analysis showed the cause to be moisture damage (coffee spill).
- _____ 10. An electronics countermeasures unit malfunctioned. Shop technician reseated all the cards and the unit checked OK.
- _____ 11. After takeoff and gear retraction, a landing gear warning light stayed on. Later, a technician adjusted a switch to correct the problem.
- _____ 12. A radio was replaced because of a built-in-test (BIT) indication. Depot failure analysis identified a bad transistor in the BIT circuit.

- _____ 13. The heads-up display malfunctioned. An engineering change was approved that should prevent reoccurrence.
- _____ 14. An aircraft made an uncommanded maneuver. A software error was found and corrected. This particular malfunction has not recurred as of this date.
- _____ 15. The GFE radar warning receiver malfunctioned and was removed. In the shop, moisture (rain) was found.
- _____ 16. After 3 months, paint began to peel from the fuselage of a new aircraft.
- _____ 17. Hail dented the leading edge of a wing. Two panels were replaced.
- _____ 18. The generator on the number 3 engine malfunctioned in flight. The unit was removed and repaired at the depot.
- _____ 19. The cause of the generator malfunction above was determined to be a faulty generator control unit, which was also removed and repaired at the depot.
- _____ 20. A technician dropped a hammer on a composite wing panel, causing de-lamination of the fiber layers.
- _____ 21. A fuel leak was corrected by tightening a fluid connector.
- _____ 22. Per tech data, a gearbox was replaced after 2000 hours of failure-free operation.
- _____ 23. Chemical vapors from the GFE battery caused severe corrosion to a hydraulic line. The line was replaced.
- _____ 24. A cut tire is discovered during a postflight inspection and is replaced.
- _____ 25. A tire, warranted for 50 landings, is finally worn beyond safe limits after accumulating 70 landings, and is replaced.
- _____ 26. During a routine, end-of-the-day inspection, a technician discovered and replaced a broken latch on an access door.
- _____ TOTAL NUMBER OF "FAILURES"